

Solvent Effect and Assignment of Bands of Absorption Spectra of Some Phenol Betaines. Part II

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Absorption spectra of N-methyl (2')-2-stilbazolium hydroxide anhydro-salt has been studied in different solvents in the region 200 nm to 650 nm. A marked relation between the absorption spectra and the hydrogen bonding capacity of the solvent has been observed in the case of anhydro-salt characteristic absorption band in the region of longer wave-lengths. Three bands at 16720, 25970 and 36230 cm^{-1} have been observed in the case of N-methyl (2'-hydroxy)-2-stilbazolium hydroxide anhydro-salt, when benzene is used as the solvent. Based on the available evidences, the band at 16720 cm^{-1} has been assigned to an intramolecular charge-transfer band. Using Platt's notations, the band at 25970 cm^{-1} has been assigned to ${}^1\text{B} \leftarrow {}^1\text{A}$, $\text{V} \rightarrow \text{N}$ ($\pi - \pi^*$) transition and at 36230 cm^{-1} to ${}^1\text{H} \leftarrow {}^1\text{A}$ ($\pi \leftarrow \pi^*$) transition.

The chemistry of anhydro-salts with reference to the phenol betaines has been reviewed by Saxena¹. The absorption spectra and assignment of the bands to different transitions of some phenol betaines have been reported recently². However no systematic study of the absorption spectra of the betaines derived from hydroxy-2-stilbazoles containing an anionic oxygen in a separate benzene nucleus, has been reported so far. In the present communication, a systematic study of the absorption spectra of N-methyl (2', 3'- and 4'-hydroxy)-2-stilbazolium hydroxide anhydro-salt, in different solvents and the probable assignments of different bands has been described and discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-methyl (2')-2-stilbazolium hydroxide anhydro-salt was prepared by the method described by Saxena *et al.*³

All measurements have been carried out on Unicam S.P. 500 spectrophotometer. All the measurements were carried out at about 25°. Plots of molar extinction coefficients (litres/mole cm) against wave numbers (cm^{-1}) for the observed bands of N-methyl (2'-hydroxy)-2-stilbazolium hydroxide anhydro-salt in (1) benzene, (2) ethanol and (3) chloroform are given in Figure I. Characteristics of different bands have been tabulated in Table I.

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Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of N-methyl-2'-hydroxy-2-stilbazolium hydroxide anhydro-salt in (1) - · - · - benzene, (2) — ethanol, and (3) - - - - chloroform.

TABLE 1

Characteristics and assignment of bands of absorption spectra of N-methyl (2'-hydroxy)-2-stilbazolium hydroxide anhydro-salt

Molecule	Band	Solvent	Band nm	position (cm ⁻¹)	Intensity max	f	Assignment
N-methyl(2'-hydroxy)-2-stilbazolium hydroxide anhydro-salt	I	benzene	598	16720	30900	.38	Intramolecular charge transfer band.
		chloroform	586	17060	36300	.34	
		ethanol	494	20240	19950	.35	
	II	benzene	385	25970	17800	.31	¹ B ← ¹ A
		chloroform	378	26460	22400	.41	V → N
		ethanol	352	28410	20400	.66	(π → π*) transition.
	III	benzene	276	36230	8900	.19	¹ H ← ¹ A
		chloroform	264	37880	11750	.27	(π → π*) transition.
		ethanol	250	40000	12600	.43	
Methiodide of N-methyl (2'-hydroxy)-2-stilbazolium hydroxide anhydro-salt.	I	ethanol	359	27860	9550		
	II	ethanol	297	33670	9120		

f values have been estimated using Jorgensen's formula.

DISCUSSION

N-methyl (2'-hydroxy)-2-stilbazolium hydroxide anhydro-salt is capable of existing in the resonating forms (a) and (b).

There is a preponderance of the form (a) over (b), as it accounts more readily the dipolar nature and deep colour of the compound³.

The parent compound, the hydrocarbon stilbene^{4,5} was chosen for the sake of discussion of its spectra with that of the betaine. Stilbazole may be considered as derived from stilbene by the replacement of one methine group ($-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$) with a trivalent nitrogen ($-\text{N}=\text{CH}-$), and are thus π -isoelectronic. The absorption spectra of these compounds therefore should have similar general features^{5,6,7}. On substitution of a methyl group on nitrogen atom and the anionic oxygen in the phenyl ring results into the desired compound, N-methyl (2'-hydroxy)-2-stilbazolium hydroxide anhydro-salt. The effect of introduction of these groups in the stilbene molecule should result into a general bathochromic shift in its absorption spectra.^{7,10} Further on account of the reduced symmetry of the compound due to substitution, the vibrational structure of the longer wave-length band is expected to be absent. Some weak bands may also appear due to excitation of the lone pair of electrons on nitrogen and oxygen atoms to higher levels.

The most striking feature in the absorption spectra of the phenol betaine under study, is the appearance of the new high intensity band in the longer wave-lengths region which is absent in the parent compound stilbene or the stilbazole. Behaviour of this band can be explained by its comparison with the spectra of the N-oxides of pyridine and quinoline^{8,9} in which case also similar effects have been observed.

The ground state of the phenol betaine may be considered as the resonance hybrid of the two structures (a) and (b). The ground state of the compound involving such a polar structure is considerably stabilised by polar solvents and by general electrostatic effects, as well as by hydrogen bonding with the anionic oxygen.¹⁰ The bathochromic shift of the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition indicates that the π^* level is less stabilised by the polar solvents; and since the excited state must also receive its predominant contribution from the polar structure (a), the difference between the ground and the excited state is expected to lie predominantly in hydrogen bonding; but the greatly reduced hydrogen bonding in the excited state would imply that the structure (b) is more important and that the oxygen atom has lost much or most of its charge. Thus the long wave-length band of N-methyl(2'-hydroxy)-2-stilbazolium hydroxide anhydro-salt which appears at 598 nm ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 30,900$) in benzene, may be assigned to an intramolecular charge transfer band.

When hydrogen bonding with the oxygen anion occurs in hydroxylic solvents, the bands are shifted back to blue and practically coincide with those of the parent compound, in acidic medium. This is what has been observed when solvent used is ethanol. Similar effects are reported in the case of N-oxides of pyridine and quinoline.^{8,9} Since the dipole-moment of the phenol betaine is expected to decrease on electronic transition, the absorption bands will be shifted to shorter wave lengths with the increase of the polarity of the solvent.^{11,12}

Assignment of the absorption bands of N-methyl (2'-hydroxy)-2-stilbazolium hydroxide hydroxide anhydro-salt :

Band I : This band is observed at 598 nm in benzene (nonpolar) ($\epsilon_{\max} = 30,900$) which shifts to 586 m μ ($\max = 36,300$) in chloroform and to 494 nm ($\max = 19,950$) in ethanol. The shift towards shorter wave length and the decrease in intensity was expected because of hydrogen bonding of the phenol betaine molecules with the hydroxylic solvent with the anionic oxygen. This band has been assigned to an intramolecular charge transfer band. In the parent compound stilbene as well as 2-stilbazole no such band is observed. The absence of the long wave length band in the methiodide of N-methyl (2'-hydroxy)-2-stilbazolium hydroxide further confirms that the band observed is a charge transfer band.

Band II : In the parent compound stilbene this band consists of four vibrational peaks at 283, 294, 307 and 320.5 m μ with ($\epsilon_{\max} = 27,950$) at 294 nm (*solvent heptane*). In the case of phenol betaine this band is observed at 385 nm ($\epsilon_{\max} = 17,800$) in benzene, showing a bathochromic shift. This is because of the effect of the substituents on the stilbene molecule, producing a bathochromic shift with the loss of the vibrational structure. This band shows a hypochromic shift with the increase in the polarity of the solvent. Thus in chloroform this band is observed at 378 nm ($\epsilon_{\max} = 22,400$) and in ethanol at 352 nm ($\epsilon_{\max} = 20,400$), which is because the dipole moment of the phenol betaine molecule is expected to decrease on electronic transitions. Using Platt's notations¹³ this band has been assigned to ${}^1B \leftarrow {}^1A$, $V \rightarrow N$ ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$) transition.

Band III : In the case of the parent compound stilbene, the band is observed at 228 nm ($\epsilon_{\max} = 16,200$) (*solvent heptane*). In the phenol betaine under study, this band is observed at 276 nm ($\epsilon_{\max} = 8900$) in benzene. Here also a bathochromic shift is observed which has been ascribed to the effect of the substituents on the parent compound viz. stilbene. This band shows a hypochromic shift in solvents of increasing polarity. Thus in chloroform it is observed at 264 nm ($\epsilon_{\max} = 11,750$) and at 250 nm in ethanol ($\epsilon_{\max} = 12,600$). This is because as in band II, the dipole moment of the molecule is expected to decrease on electronic transition. Using Platt's notation,¹³ this band has been assigned to ${}^1H \leftarrow {}^1A$ ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$) transition.

Absorption spectra of (3'- and 4'- hydroxy)-2-stilbazolium hydroxide anhydro-salt, studied through their methiodides in alkaline ethanol show similar general features.

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